

INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES AND ITS COMPONENTS

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Abstract: The article discusses the issues related to the independent work of students as a means of developing linguistic competencies and its components. As it is known that, among the factors contributing to the formation of creative activity of students, one of the leading places is occupied by independent work. Only purposeful, systematic independent work of each student makes it possible to deeply assimilate knowledge, develop and consolidate skills, and transform them into appropriate mental work skills.

Keywords: independent work, creative activity, educational system, skill.

The leading principle of building a modern educational system is the differentiation of education, which has become a means of solving the problem of satisfying the interests, inclinations and needs of students, and a stimulus for the development of their creative activity. Recently, there has been a tendency to increase the number of educational establishments and classes in the humanities. Under these conditions, there is a weakening of students' interest in mathematical subjects.

Therefore, the main principle of teacher's work is the organization of students' activities aimed at developing not only subject knowledge and skills, but also at developing students' independence and creative activity.

A significant contribution to the development of the theory of independence and creative activity of students in the learning process was made by prominent teachers Babansky Yu.K., Danilov M.A., Esipov B.P., Lerner I.Ya., Makhmutov M.I., Ogorodnikov I.T. ., Pidkasisty P.I., Skatkin M.N. and etc.; psychologists Bogoyavlensky D.N., Vygotsky L.S., Galperin P.Ya., Davydov V.V., Zankov L.V., Matyushkin A.M., Menchinskaya N.A., Leontyev A.N., Rubinstein S.L., Elkonin D.B., Esaulov A.F. etc. These studies have shown that one of the effective means of developing students' independence and creative activity is independent work.

Drozina V.V. formulated the main provisions of the theory and practice of organizing creative independent activity of students. The essence of the concept of "independent work", goals, objectives, didactic principles, functions of independent work, forms and methods of its organization in the learning process are fully and deeply analyzed in the studies: Garunova M.G., Korolkova B.E., Orlovsky V.G., Pidkasisty P.I., Tsukar A.Ya., Chikantseva N.I. and etc.

The relevance of this problem is indisputable, since knowledge, skills, beliefs, spirituality cannot be transferred from teacher to student, resorting only to words. This process includes familiarization, perception, independent processing, awareness and acceptance of these skills and concepts.

During the learning process, the teacher's task is not only to provide solid knowledge provided by the program, but also to develop the independence and active thinking of students.

Independent work is such a cognitive educational activity when the sequence of the student's thinking, his mental and practical operations and actions depend and are determined by the student himself. The presence of independent work is necessary in lessons, including in mathematics lessons, as they train the will, cultivate efficiency, attention, and discipline students. In mathematics lessons, a teacher needs to rely on students' independent work, independent reasoning, and inference.

Independent work is a method that greatly helps the teacher to determine the abilities of students. Working independently, the student must gradually master such general techniques of independent work as presenting the purpose of the work, performing it, checking, and correcting errors.

The research problem is due to contradictions:

- between the mandatory level of mathematical training fixed in the mathematics program and the student’s inability to achieve a certain sufficiently high level of independence, which opens up the opportunity to cope with various tasks and discover new things in the process of solving mathematical problems.

- between the absence in the methodology of mathematics of a generalized approach and recommendations for organizing a system of independent work and the program provided for the study of mathematics;

- between the minimum level of mandatory requirements for students and the desire for a more complete development of the mathematical abilities of students.

Over time, with the systematic organization of independent work in the classroom and combining it with various types of homework on the subject, students develop stable independent work skills. As a result, students spend significantly less time to complete work of approximately the same volume and degree of difficulty compared to students in classes in which independent work is practically not organized or is carried out irregularly. This allows you to gradually increase the pace of studying program material, increase the time for solving problems, performing experimental work and other types of creative work.

This feature of goal setting has didactic significance for teaching activities - the teacher can focus on the presented nomenclature when organizing and independent work of students. At the same time, it is important to teach the student to set goals for himself. In different classes, during the analysis of new material, when checking assignments, it is advisable to first lead the student to an understanding of the teacher’s goal, and then to independently setting his own goals that have a personal meaning for him. An important condition for this is that the goals of students must be realistically achievable.

The general goal of students’ independent work when studying mathematics is the formation of students’ mathematical thinking.

This goal of independent work in the study of mathematics is specified in the tasks of independent work on each topic, among which priority ones are highlighted.

To achieve these goals, the conditions for organizing independent work are of great importance, which can significantly increase its efficiency. These include individualization, which includes:

- increasing the proportion of intensive work with more prepared students;
- dividing the lesson into mandatory and creative parts (for everyone trying to independently cope with more difficult and, most importantly, non-standard tasks, additional questions, educational problem situations, etc.);
- regular consultations with trainees;
- comprehensive and timely information about the thematic content of independent work, deadlines, the need for auxiliary aids, forms, methods of control and evaluation of the final results with mandatory comparison with the expected ones.

These conditions determine the use of a person-centered approach to learning, which contributes to the full disclosure of the abilities of each student and subsequent creative development.

Students who study independently throughout class have high learning motivations for self-improvement, self-learning, self-education, and self-organization. This process covers the methodical planning of self-directed learning exercises. The flexibility to choose the format and subject matter of independent work may greatly boost students' interest in the topic and have a positive impact on the quality of the learning process.

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